

THE ESTIMATION OF ANEURIN BY THIOCHROME REACTION WITH PULFRICH PHOTOMETER.

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A modification of Jansen's method for the estimation of aneurin in different substances by converting the aneurin to thiochrome is described. It consists in carrying out the oxidation of aneurin in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and later on in estimating the thiochrome by means of analysis with quartz lamp and Pulfrich's photometer. The results agree with the findings of other workers using Cohen fluorometer.

The fact that aneurin is oxidised to thiochrome (Peters, *Nature*, 1935, 135, 107) in an alkaline medium (Barger *et al*, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 2257) has been utilised by Jansen (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1936, 55, 1046) for quantitative determination of aneurin. It has later on been modified by Westenbrink and Goudsmit (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1937, 56, 803) for measuring the same in urine, but undoubtedly the same can be extended for measuring aneurin in other substances, normally liquid. Pyke has used the same method for determining aneurin in solid substances where he simply powders the substance and dissolves in water containing 1% hydrochloric acid and uses the liquid recovered from the same (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 1958). Karrer and Kubli (1937, 20, 369) used the method of Jansen and by some modification changed the fluorescing colour from rich blue to violet and also the intensity of the fluorescence was increased considerably which enabled them to measure the intensity with naked eye with another standard. Jansen oxidised the aneurin in an atmosphere of nitrogen gas and measured the fluorescence of the resulting thiochrome by means of a Cohen fluorometer, in which the fluorescence is converted into electric current by means of a photoelectric cell and led off to a ballistic galvanometer, in the mirror of which a beam of light was incident. The movement of the light is recorded over a graduated scale. In the present communication a method is described by which the fluorescence itself is being measured by means of a Pulfrich photometer using quartz analysis lamp as the source of light. The nitrogen gas is replaced by carbon dioxide which gives stability to the thiochrome formed and is also easily procurable. The amount of isobutanol required is much less and so adds to the economy where large number of estimations are to be made.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

For each estimation 60 and 75 c. c. of the liquid to be examined were taken and diluted with water to 240 and 300 c. c. respectively. It was brought to a p_H of about 3 by adding hydrochloric acid. Ten centrifuge tubes were taken and four of them received 30 c.c. of the solution in each tube. The remaining 180 c.c. were divided in two parts and mixed with different amounts of aneurin, usually between 10-50 γ , 30 c.c. of the solution were then put in each of the six tubes. Fuller's earth was added in 100 mg. parts to each tube, stirred for about 3-5 minutes and centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was thrown off and Fuller's earth was washed first with distilled water which was made acid with hydrochloric acid to a p_H of about 3, and then with absolute alcohol or rectified spirit. The earth was then dried in an oven at a temperature of about 80-100°. The aneurin, which was adsorbed on the Fuller's earth, was then eluted by 2 c. c. of methyl alcohol while a stream of pure carbon dioxide was passed through the mixture from a carbon dioxide cylinder. After about two minutes 1 c. c. of 30% caustic potash solution was added and at intervals of half a minute 1% potassium ferricyanide, 2 c. c. of water, and 3 c. c. of *isobutyl* alcohol were added and finally after 1 minute the tube was corked and centrifuged for a short time, till the *isobutyl* alcohol layer was clear. It is to be emphasised here that till before corking carbon dioxide was continuously passed through the solution. Amount of potassium ferricyanide required for formation of maximum amount of thiochrome is variable and depends both on the amount of aneurin and the nature of foreign substances present in the test solution and therefore different amounts were added in different tubes. It has been found by Jansen *et al* (*loc. cit.*) that the amount of 1% potassium ferricyanide required lies within the limit of 0.6-1 c. c. So each set of tubes got 0.6, 0.8 and 1 c. c. of potassium ferricyanide, except that in the first set of four solutions without added aneurin, the fourth one had no potassium ferricyanide and served as a control. The estimation of the thiochrome and also of the aneurin was then carried out by means of Pulfrich photometer and analysis quartz lamp. The bulb of the lamp was brought to a level at right angles with the cell-holder of the photometer.

A filter, filled with 10% copper sulphate solution, was used with the mercury. As it is very important to have equal illumination, light from that portion of the bulb was used only which was seen glowing equally bright

through the filter, and could be conveniently marked off with a marking pencil over the metal frame of the filter. As with fluorometry it is not possible to have the so-called absolute measurements of colorimetry, it is essential to have another fluorescing solution whose spectral energy would approach the test solution as much as possible and at the same time be easily available. With the photometer a piece of uranium glass was provided which was more green fluorescing than blue, while the fluorescence of the thiochrome was rich blue and so could not be utilised for the purpose. Quinine sulphate in acid solution fluoresces both green and rich blue, and is easily available and quite stable at least for several months as far as fluorescence is concerned. For most of the cases it will be sufficient to use 1 mg % of the quinine sulphate solution bringing the p_H of the solution to 3 with dilute hydrochloric acid. It has been found that greater fluorescence is obtained with thinner cells. Cells, 2.47-2.50 mm. thick, have been found to be quite suitable in fluorometry. The two cells filled with the quinine sulphate solution were placed in the cell-holder till equal illumination was obtained for both. One of the cells was cleaned and filled with the test solution containing the formed thiochrome and placed in the cell-holder, while the other cell containing quinine solution was lying in the other cell-holder. The drum on that side, on which the solution fluoresces, was kept fully open, while the drum on the other side was adjusted till the intensities of light were as much as possible equal on both sides of the field of illumination. The readings were then noted in terms of the percentage of light. This is a case of real fluorescence and so no question of extinction of light arises and we do not require to note the extinction coefficient which is found in red letters by the side of the scale noting light transmitted in percentage. It will further be found from the following data that the reading is exactly proportional to the concentration of thiochrome and so of aneurin contained in the test solution. In the case of solutions containing much suspension it must be centrifuged off before proceeding with the estimation, for otherwise they will be precipitated with the Fuller's earth and when finally dried may form a hard mass very difficult to be suspended in methanol during elution of the vitamin. The foreign substances also, when present in large quantities, interfere with the more precise determinations. In the case of solid substances they are first powdered and soaked in water, brought to p_H 3 by keeping with hydrochloric acid for about 24 hours, shaking now and then or preferably stirring continually by means of an electric stirrer. Afterwards it was filtered and the filtrate used for estimation of aneurin. Where the substance is supposed to contain very little aneurin it is

better to take at least 100 g. of the substance and dissolve it in 400 c.c. of the acidulated water. The following are the results of some of the determinations in various substances.

With pure aneurin solutions containing 10, 20, 25, 27 and 50 γ , keeping the drum fully open on this side, *i.e.*, at 100, the quinine values were 5'9; 5, 13, 18 and 25'5 which are nearly proportional to aneurin contents.

S A M P L E I.

Urine diluted to four times its volume.

Quinine value.	Urine value.	1% Pot. ferricyanide..	
3'37	100	0 c.c.	
3'5	100	0'8	
4'0	100	1'0	
	Urine value + 97B ₁ .		
4'0	100	0'6	
4'25	100	0'8	
5'2	100	1'0	
	Urine value + 277B ₁ .		
5'0	100	0'6	
5'5	100	0'8	
7'5	100	1'0	
Blank	Urine.	Urine + 97B ₁ .	Urine + 277B ₁ .
(without Pot. ferricyanide)			
3'37	4	5'2	7'5
Urine (blank)	= 0'63 = A		
Urine + 97B ₁ - urine (blank)	= 1'2 = B		
Urine + 277B ₁ - urine (blank)	= 3'5 = C		

It will be seen that C is about three times B corresponding with the amount of aneurin added. Now A represents aneurin contained in 100 c.c. of the dilute urine, therefore in the original urine the aneurin would be represented by $0'63 \times 4$, *i.e.*, 2.52% of the fluorescence of the quinine. The percentage of fluorescence of quinine represented by 1'2 and 3'5 represents respectively the fluorescence of thiochrome formed from 9 and 27 γ of

aneurin. Hence the urine contained 197 aneurin per 100 c.c. It is important to note that the person (a vegetarian) used to take little water and the urine was scanty and concentrated.

S A M P L E II.

Urine diluted to four times its volume.

Quinine value.	Urine value.	1% Pot. ferricyanide
2.75	100	0 c.c.
3.37	100	0.6
3.16	100	0.8
3.3	100	1.0
	Urine value + 8γ B ₁ .	
4.125	100	0.6
4.125	100	0.8
4.75	100	1.0
	Urine value + 18γ B ₁ .	
5.5	100	0.6
6	100	0.8
7.25	100	1.0
Urine + 8γ aneurin - urine	= 1.38 = A	
Urine + 18γ aneurin - urine	= 3.88 = B	
Urine (blank)	= 0.62 = C	

It is found that B is about two and half times A corresponding to the aneurin added. The figures 1.38 and 3.88 represent respectively 8 and 18 aneurin so that 0.62×4 or 2.48 represents about 147 aneurin and is contained in 100 c.c. of original urine.

S A M P L E III.

Urine was diluted to four times its volume. From now only one reading will be given for each series corresponding with the maximum fluorescence obtained with the optimal amount of potassium ferricyanide.

Quinine value.	Urine value.	1% Pot. ferricyanide.
3.37	100	0.8 c.c.
2.7	100	
	Urine value + 197B ₁ .	
8.0	100	
	Urine value + 387B ₁ .	
13.25	100	

Urine (blank) = 0.67 = A

Urine + 197B₁ - urine = 4.63 = B

Urine + 387B₁ - urine = 9.88 = C

The figures in C are about twice those in B corresponding to the aneurin content added so that 197B₁ is represented by 4.63 or the aneurin contained in the original urine is about 10.57 aneurin per 100 c.c.

S A M P L E IV.

Urine diluted to four times.

Quinine value.	Urine value.	1% Pot. ferricyanide.
2.6	100	0 c.c.
3.12	100	0.8
	Urine value + 197B ₁ .	
6.5	100	1
	Urine value + 387B ₁ .	
9.0	100	1
Blank	Urine + 197B ₁ .	Urine + 387B ₁ .
2.6	3.12 6.5	9

Urine (blank) = 0.52 = A

Urine + 197B₁ - urine = 3.38 = B

Urine + 387B₁ - urine = 6.38 = C

Readings in C are about twice those in B corresponding to the aneurin added. As per calculation above the aneurin per 100 c.c. of the urine is 11.57.

Polished rice.

100 G. of the rice powder soaked in 600 c.c. of water (p_H 3) for 24 hours with shaking at intervals, afterwards filtered and used for aneurin estimation.

Quinine value.	Rice soln.	1% Pot. ferricyanide.
2.87	100	0 c.c.
3.5	100	1
	Rice soln. + 20 γ B ₁ .	
6.5	100	1
	Rice soln. + 41 γ B ₁ .	
8.25	100	1

Therefore 100 g. of the sample of rice contain about 33 γ aneurin or 16.5 international units.

Carrot.

100 G. of the minced substance were soaked in 400 c.c. of water (p_H 3) for 24 hours with shaking at intervals, filtered and the filtrate used for estimation of aneurin.

Quinine value.	Carrot soln.	1% Pot. ferricyanide.
3.6	100	0 c.c.
5	100	0.8
	Carrot soln. + 15 γ B ₁ .	
7.2	100	0.8
	Carrot soln. + 30 γ B ₁ .	
9.7	100	0.8

Carrot soln. (blank) = 1.4 = A

Carrot soln. + 15 γ B₁ - carrot (blank) = 2.2 = B

Carrot soln. + 30 γ B₁ - carrot (blank) = 4.7 = C

Therefore 100 g. of the substance contain about 40 γ aneurin or 20 I.U.

In a similar way aneurin contents of some other substances were determined. A sample of bread was found to have 6.5 γ aneurin per 100 g. of the substance. A sample powder designated as vitamin B complex by a Calcutta firm contained 264 γ aneurin per 100 g. of the substance. This was undoubtedly a sample of aneurin adsorbed on Fuller's earth and as such the estimation was not done in the usual way. 0.5 G. of the substance was put in each of the 10 centrifuge tubes and four of them treated with methanol, KOH solution, etc., from the very beginning. Three of the rest

were treated with 12.5γ aneurin and the other three with 25γ aneurin, the solution was centrifuged off, washed with water at p_{H} 3, and alcohol and dried at 100°. Then the estimation was done as usual starting with methanol. Two of the three preparations were liquid and estimation was made as usual. One of them contained 34.6γ aneurin per 100 c.c. and the other contained 60γ aneurin per 100 c.c. of the substance.

D I S C U S S I O N.

From the above results we are in a position to say that aneurin can be estimated by the present modification of Jansen's method using a Pulfrich photometer instead of a fluorometer and the reasons are as follows: (1) the readings obtained are very approximately proportional to the aneurin present with pure solutions; (2) with impure solutions the readings obtained after adding different amounts of aneurin subtracted from the reading without addition of aneurin are closely proportional to the amount of aneurin added; (3) the aneurin contents of carrot, polished rice, etc., agree with the biological values; (4) the aneurin values of human urine found here vary from 10.5 to 19γ per 100 c.c. Westenbrink and Goudsmit (*Ext. Arch. Neerl. Physiol.*, 1937, 22, 319 and *Nederl. Tijdschr. Geneesk.*, 1938, 82, 518) found 5.20γ aneurin per 100 c.c. Karrer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 1147) found 10.7-14γ aneurin per 100 c.c. of urine. The advantage with this method is that it does not require a special instrument for the estimation and the use of carbon dioxide instead of nitrogen gives stability to the thiochrome formed which has a distinct advantage in estimating the fluorescence in ultraviolet light which otherwise is destroyed quickly, and besides carbon dioxide is a much more common thing in a laboratory than nitrogen.

Compared with the electrical measurement of the fluorescence there is one disadvantage with the present method and that is the personal factor involved in matching the intensities. But errors that arise in this connection have been greatly reduced by increasing the fluorescence of the test solution simply by decreasing the quantity of isobutanol from 13 c.c. to 3 or 4 c.c. which is also appreciably economical when aneurin contents of large number of samples are to be determined.